

Urban Heat Health Risk Index

Demonstrated as part of the Open Geospatial Consortium

Climate & Disasters Resilience Pilot 2024

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Urban Heat Health Risk Index

Introduction

A health data analytics company, HSR.health specializes in utilizing geospatial technologies, health, social, and environmental data, ML/AI techniques, and novel public health models to allow organizations to anticipate future health risks to their operations, assets, and the populations they serve. We provide insights allowing the public health and emergency response decision makers to mitigate disaster-induced health and medical needs and allocate resources to treat the affected.

With the goal of striving for health equity and improving global public health, this pilot project is significant given as global temperatures rise, extreme heat event frequency, severity, intensity, and overall effects have increased, heavily impacting public health. This project aims to find potential solutions to this public health concern.

Through the 2024 Climate and Disaster Resilience Pilot, HSR.health developed an Urban Heat Health Risk Index that identifies in advance the health and medical needs of an extreme heat-impacted population. The pilot was funded by the U.S. Department of Homeland Security (DHS), the National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (NGA), and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and managed by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).

The Urban Heat Health Risk Index aims to provide a useful indicator of where vulnerable populations are to inform resource and personnel allocation before, during, and after a response effort. The Risk Index models the effects of extreme heat exposure to assess the risks of adverse health outcomes, including potential deaths and hospitalizations down to the Census Tract, street, building, and even the apartment building level. This information enables public health, emergency response, as well as communities themselves to have greater visibility into and more precise estimates of the overall risk posture to support effective, customized response strategies by neighborhood.

This indicator focuses specifically on communities with a unique risk exposure that is often not considered. HSR.health's Urban Heat-Health Risk Index incorporates the heat differential between the upper floors of tall residential buildings versus ground temperatures. Upper floors of buildings that rise above and stand out from their surroundings have a different solar radiation exposure. It's harder to get cool air and water to those floors, and more difficult to evacuate. Our pilot will assess the risk to occupants and provide a more complete view of climate change-caused rising temperatures on health outcomes and its economic impacts.

Additionally, HSR.health has developed a heat-related hospitalization estimate applied to two (2) scenarios within an identified pilot area on Manhattan Island in New York City:

- 100 Degree Fahrenheit weather for 5 consecutive days as measured from Central Park with 40% humidity at the hottest part of the day.
- The same weather conditions with the addition of 2 days with no power.

The Urban Heat Health Risk Index aligns with our contribution to the 2023 Disasters pilot with our Drought Health Risk Index and Wildland Fire Health Risk Index in addition to our Hurricane Health Risk Index (2019 DP, 2022 DP, and 2023 Federated Marine Spatial Data Infrastructure Pilot) and the Bioaccumulation Health Risk Index (2023 Federated Marine Spatial Data Infrastructure Pilot) in serving as a demonstrator for industry use.

Health Impacts of Extreme Heat

A particular worrisome effect of climate change on human health and welfare will be its effect on the creation of deadly heat waves (Bojunda 2021). Heat waves are increasing in frequency and intensity and undeniably related to climate change processes. There's a direct link between climate change and deadly heat waves. A study by the World Weather Attribution looking at the deadly 2017 Southern European heat waves, found that climate change increased its chance of occurrence by a factor of 10. (Kew et al., 2018) A study by the Union of Concerned Scientists in 2019 found that by middle of the 21st Century, the United States will see the number of days with 105-degree heat index temperatures to triple (UCUSA Website) and another study in 2017 found that for every 1 degree Celsius of increased global warming, we will see the number of heat-wave days increase from 4 to 34 days per season (Perkins-Kirkpatrick et al., 2017) Extreme heat is defined as temperatures that are significantly higher than the average for a particular area in combination with increased humidity (Baldwin et al., 2023). The exposure to extreme

heat pushes the limits of individuals' ability to thermoregulate, which can lead to a host of different symptoms and conditions, including possible mortality. The potential effects of extreme heat include increases in heat stroke and related conditions, cardiovascular disease, respiratory disease, amongst others. Extreme heat differentially affects different age groups, races, social determinants, pre-existing health conditions, and overall health profiles, leading to more vulnerable populations (Stone et al., 2010).

Social and Community Determinants of Health

The following factors influence the degree to susceptibility to adverse health outcomes from exposure to extreme heat.

Age

Age-based populations most vulnerable to extreme heat are adults aged 65 and older (Fouillet et al, 2006) and children 0-4 years of age (Wöhl et al., 2019). Young children have underdeveloped thermoregulatory systems and are more likely to dehydrate during extreme heat events, and older adults have attenuated thermoregulatory control and thus experience a decrease in sweating (Baldwin et al., 2023).

Land cover

Prior research has shown the association between extreme heat vulnerability and percentage of non-green space. There is, of course, a widely accepted association between percentage of non-green space and poverty, which may contribute to an increased vulnerability on its own (Reid et al., 2009).

Under Federal Poverty Line

Those under the Federal Poverty Line are more likely to be vulnerable due to extreme heat due to the quality of their neighborhoods and housing situations, decreased likelihood of having air conditioning, and increased distance to medical centers (Reid et al., 2009).

Living situation

Prior research found that the indicator of living alone has been associated with increased risk of extreme heat vulnerability. It is believed that individuals experiencing heat-related adverse health symptoms in this housing status do not have roommates to notice and intervene as the condition worsens (Reid et al., 2009).

Pregnancy and perinatal factors

While acute heat stress affects pregnant women due to decreased ability for thermoregulation, a more pressing issue with extreme heat and pregnant women is due to the developing fetus. Body temperature

over 39 degrees Celsius is considered to be a teratogen and can lead to adverse fetal outcomes including miscarriage or stillborn in rare cases. (Syed et al., 2022)

Physical health conditions

People with preexisting chronic health conditions have been found to be at increased susceptibility to complications due to extreme heat events, including those with cardiovascular disease, diabetes, renal disease, nervous disorders, cerebrovascular disease, and pulmonary conditions (Reid et al, 2012). People with these conditions are at higher risk of mortality due to extreme heat.

Mental health conditions

People with mental health conditions have also been found to be at higher risk of susceptibility to extreme heat, including individuals with depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, and schizophrenia. The etiology of this increased vulnerability is unclear; however, it may also be the susceptibility is a result of taking medications prescribed for these conditions, which can inhibit diaphoresis and thus attenuate a person’s ability to thermoregulate.

Methodology

This pilot involved the development of two, related indicators. In addition to the Urban Heat Health Risk Index, a Hospitalization Estimate was developed to inform health systems, public health, and communities of the anticipated patient load due to exposure to extreme temperatures. Both indicators enable planning for and provide guidance on when to adopt mitigation measure to address and avoid such exposure.

Study Area

The pilot study area, shown in Figure 1, is defined as a portion of Northern Manhattan Island above W 110th Street, within New York City, New York.

The residential building at 119 W 116th Street, located within the pilot study area and shown in Figure 2, was modeled to assess the heat differential to which it and its residents are exposed due to the extra solar radiation it receives.

Figure 1: Pilot Study Area.

Figure 2: Residential building modeled for excess heat exposure.

Urban Heat Health Risk Index

We use multiple machine learning, artificial intelligence, and data science techniques in the development of our various health risk indices. For the Urban Heat Health Risk Index, we leveraged a weighted combination of the prevalence of social and health factors that describe the vulnerability to extreme heat. Based on a review of the public health literature, these risk factors include low income, internet / phone access, over the age of 65, under the age of 5, chronic kidney disease, and diabetes prevalence.

Heat Hospitalization Estimate

In addition, we have developed an estimate of heat related hospitalizations through a combination of the Urban Heat Health Risk Index and extreme heat data from NOAA, 3D Building modeling data from GISMO, Safe Soft, and their collaborators, historical data from the National Death Index (NDI), and existing heat related hospitalization data for NYC.

To estimate hospitalizations related to extreme heat exposure, a spatial analysis of temperature was conducted using data from over 30 weather stations managed by the Weather Forecast Office in New York, NY (WFO OKX). This office is responsible for all of New York City, as well as parts of northeastern New Jersey and southern Connecticut. Each day was scored based on its maximum temperature minus 80°F. Days with temperatures below 80°F were assigned a score of zero. To account for the cumulative effects of prolonged heat exposure, half of the previous day's score was added to the current day's score. In this way, scores during prolonged heat waves would progressively increase, though the impact lessens over time.

Despite daily inconsistencies in temperature distribution, the aggregated scores over the year demonstrated a clear correlation with hospitalization data. Due to limited time-series data on hospitalizations, heat-related health impacts were also estimated using excess death calculations based on weekly and county-specific counts from the NDI.

Further analysis through regression showed the strongest correlation between excess deaths and high temperatures in individuals over 55 years of age, especially those with ICD-10 codes for Diabetes mellitus (E10-E14), Hypertensive diseases (I10-I15), and Ischemic heart diseases (I20-I25). Gender-specific analysis revealed that men had a slightly stronger association between deaths and high temperatures compared to women; however, the difference was not significant enough to justify excluding women from the analysis. Daily temperature data were resampled to weekly intervals to align with the temporal granularity of the NDI death counts.

Scenario 2 Estimate

To assess the impact of an extended power outage on extreme heat resilience, we analyzed excess death rates during August 2003—a period of the last widespread, prolonged blackout in New York City—and compared these rates to those from the same month in other years. Notably, during the outage from

August 14th to 16th, 2003, deaths using the same ICD-10 codes were 8.3% higher than the average (659 compared to 604), which falls within one standard deviation of the mean.

A study performed in 2012 looking at the August 2003 power outage, enabled by approved access to daily mortality data, revealed a significant 25% increase in deaths from disease during this period, estimating about 90 excess deaths (Anderson & Bell 2012). Moreover, accidental deaths surged by 122%, contributing to an overall all-cause mortality increase of 28% (Anderson & Bell 2012). These numbers derived from unsuppressed data are likely more accurate and form a better baseline to estimate increases in hospitalization and mortality during a blackout.

Indicator Visualization and Persistent Demonstrator

To facilitate access to the health risk index we have built and leveraged our Open GeoMD Platform, a Multi-stack, Cloud-native, Health-focused Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) and shown in Figure 3. The indicators on the Open GeoMD Platform are accessible through direct download and multiple OGC standards including but not limited to WMS, WFS, and the OGC Features API.

The [Urban Heat Health Risk Index](#) and [Heat Hospitalization Estimate](#) for the New York and New Jersey Core Based Statistical Area are available as a persistent demonstrator on the Open GeoMD Platform.

Figure 3: Open GeoMD Platform.

Workflow

Figure 4 below illustrates the workflow for the Urban Heat Health Risk Index and the Heat Hospitalization Estimate, including the input data required and sources used in this effort, as well as the end users these indicators support.

Figure 4: Urban Heat Health Risk Index and Hospitalization Estimates Workflow.

Results

Based on the growing body of public health literature on heat exposure risk, Table 1 below identifies the key risk factors found to be most vulnerable and the number of individuals of such factors within the pilot study areas.

Table 1: At Risk Population within the Study Area.

Population	65+ population	< 5 years old	Income < \$25,000	Disabled	Chronic Kidney Disease
609,000	88,000	31,000	68,000	128,000	16,000

Figure 5 below show the Urban Heat Health Risk Index (left) and the Heat Hospitalization Estimate (right) for the study area.

Figure 5: Urban Heat Health Risk Index and Heat Hospitalization Estimates.

Of the 609,000 people within the study area for Scenario 1 (a 5-day extreme heat event with no blackout) the estimated number of people requiring hospitalizations due to extreme heat are 1064. For Scenario 2 (a 5-day extreme heat event with a power blackout on days 4 and 5) the estimated number of people requiring hospitalizations due to extreme heat increase to 1318. The range of estimated excess deaths for Scenario 1 lies between 11-92 and for Scenario 2 between 14-114 individuals.

Table 2: Estimated Impacts from Extreme Heat across Pilot Study Area and Scenarios.

Estimated Impacts	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
At High Risk	60,900	609,000
Hospitalizations	1064	1318
Deaths	11-92	14-114

Further discussion on the process of calculation on excess death risk appears in Appendix C. It is important to note that these findings are based on deaths as officially reported in the U.S. National Death Index. Guidance on reporting the cause of death has been set at a time when exposure to extreme heat was not a common occurrence – this phenomenon is present in the current environment due to impacts from climate change and other man-made factors. It may be time for the CDC to update guidance on recognizing heat as a contributing factor to a fatality. This is discussed further in Appendix B.

Residential Building at 119 W 116th Street

New York City maintains robust modeling on its built environment, including this residential apartment building. Based on this information (Figure 6) along with the solar arc calculated for this position and

shadow analysis at 3pm (Figure 7), it was identified that slightly over 21% (.214) of this building is sunlit at this time of day – and therefore approximately 64 of the building’s 300 residents are exposed to excess heat.

Figure 6: NYC Information on Pilot Residential Building.

Figure 7: Solar Arc of Residential Building Modeled in Pilot.

This building is located within Census Tract 218 in New York County with a population of 5,756 and an Urban Heat Health Risk Index with a normalized value of 60.75 – which is considered high risk. The purpose of establishing a numeric value is to enable comparison across regions.

The incorporation of the additional risk to the 64 residents (which represent 1.11% of the overall Census Tract population) exposed to increased heat due to the layout of their building, increases the normalized value increases to 60.89 – a 2.3% increase. This suggests that the heat risk from residing in a tall building can have an outsized impact on the overall risk. As this is one building within the Census Tract, the balance of buildings must be considered to fully assess the overall risk to the population. The modeling and solar arc analysis was performed by Extreme Heat Team member Safe Soft.

This information on a city-wide basis will provide emergency response, public health, and health systems greater and more granular information on the overall risk posture of the population to extreme heat exposure.

In future pilots, we recommend repeating the Solar Arc analysis in order to cover a full solar cycle and more fully assess heat exposure as well as opportunities for cooling. The full city street and census block can also be assessed to include aspect, vegetations, tree cover, as well as building materials and HVAC system.

Inflection Point

Analysis of data from New York City as well as other cities experiencing heat waves suggest an inflection point past which the risk of death rises in an exponential fashion, as shown in Figure 8. For example, twice as many heart attacks are reported to have occurred in periods of extreme heat.

Figure 8: Hospitalization relationship with wet bulb temperature (left) and deaths relationship with humidex (right).

It may be important to gain a better understanding of this inflection point as it may serve as an indicator for heat warnings to the public.

Utilization of the Urban Heat Health Risk Index by End Users

The Urban Heat Health Risk Index serves as a crucial tool for health professionals, policymakers, and first responders in managing extreme heat scenarios. The Risk Index can aid in determining whether there are sufficient cooling centers in high-risk areas, support the design of educational campaigns to inform vulnerable populations about their heat-related risks, and help in planning home wellness checks. Such checks are particularly critical for the elderly and vulnerable individuals, those dependent on dialysis and other routing medical care, those in living conditions that are exposed to greater heat, as well as those living alone.

Limitations and Considerations

The primary limitation of the estimated hospitalization analysis stems from the limited data on heat-related hospitalizations across New York City. The available data was an aggregation of heat-related deaths over a five-year period, presenting significant challenges and assumptions when attempting to estimate hospitalizations for a specific five-day extreme heat event.

Given these constraints, the analysis was conducted under several key assumptions:

- **Proportional Relationship:** The relationship between heat-related hospitalizations and excess deaths during high temperatures is assumed to be proportionally similar. The estimate is further limited by how deaths are recorded in the National Death Index, which follows different processes across the country at both the state and local levels.

- Heat Risk Index Consistency: The Heat Risk Index is presumed to have a consistent relationship with both hospitalizations and excess deaths.
- Stable Distribution: The distribution of hospitalizations is assumed to be similar across multiple years.
- Operational Continuity: Hospitals and nursing homes are expected to function normally with backup generators, as mandated by New York law, for a minimum of 72 hours.

These assumptions are necessary due to the limited data and play a critical role in the analysis, potentially affecting its accuracy and applicability to specific heat events.

Recommendations

The Urban Heat Health Risk Index and Hospitalization Estimate can broadly aid emergency response and public health efforts, we offer the following specific recommendations for the New York City. These do not reflect the entirety of guidance these indicators can offer New York City, or to other cities that may deploy one or both indicators.

- Cooling centers

We recommend the strategic placement of cooling centers: 8 on the main island and an additional center on Randalls and Wards Island.

Given that much of NYC relies on the subway system, which ceases operation during total blackouts, understanding pedestrian mobility in extreme heat is essential. The CDC notes that heat stroke can develop within 10 to 15 minutes of exposure to extreme conditions. Considering the average walking speed is 3 mph, most residents can safely travel approximately half a mile within this time frame. In Manhattan's grid layout, a half-mile straight path translates to about a 15-minute walk, potentially extending up to three-quarters of a mile due to street layout.

However, residents with disabilities and the elderly might require vehicular transportation for even short distances. With the capacity for most residents to walk, strategic planning can prioritize those who need assistance, regardless of distance. Given Manhattan's maximum width of 2 miles, positioning cooling centers no more than a mile apart near the island's center — aligned parallel to the coast — ensures all residents are within half a mile of a center. This setup not only facilitates access but also prioritizes inland residents who have fewer options to cool down using water.

To effectively cover the entire area, eight cooling centers would be needed on the main island, with an additional center on Randalls and Wards Island. This distribution ensures comprehensive accessibility for all residents during extreme heat events, enhancing the city's resilience and public safety. It will be important to assess the capacity of each cooling center, their times of operation, and whether backup power is available in the case of a power blackout.

- Replicate the Urban Heat Health Risk Index to cities and regions beyond the pilot area

Heat is rising in large swaths of the country and world due to climate change and other human factors, increasing the value of an early warning to guide response efforts globally to locally that such an index offers.

- Deploy the Urban Heat Health Risk Index at a hyperlocal level

A city-wide deployment of the Urban Heat Health Risk Index can aid overall public health response. In addition, we recommend deployment in specific locations, such as an apartment building complex or a warehouse so that residents and workers can have visibility into and make decisions on the heat risks to which they are exposed.

As the analysis of the residential building at 119 W 116th Street showed, buildings themselves contribute to heat exposure and should be considered in understanding the overall heat risk for the community, as well as within the building itself. For instance, south-facing apartments will have more solar exposure than north facing apartments.

- Identify populations who will benefit most from mitigations for a health perspective

In resource constrained environments, decisions often must be made as to who is most at risk and who will benefit the most from a particular mitigation. The Urban Heat Health Risk Index can provide this level as input for decision makers to ultimately allocate mitigation measures as they deem most appropriate.

- Integrate with evacuation planning efforts

In the event that heat rises to or past the point where other mitigation efforts become untenable, municipalities or broader regions, as well as families, may need to consider evacuations, or potentially, [living underground](#). The Future Work section includes a discussion on possible thought processes around the use of evacuations to address extreme heat.

- Integration with resource allocation and logistics efforts

Integration of the Urban Heat Health Risk Index with the Medical Supply Needs Index, demonstrated in DP21 in Peru and Louisiana, can identify the resources required to aid the vulnerable populations given the duration and severity of the heat wave anticipated.

Future Work

This section includes suggestions for future Climate and Disaster Resilience Pilots as well as for cities implementing one or both of these indicators.

- Develop a heat-health risk rating score for specific conditions that are exacerbated by exposure to extreme heat.

Several clinical conditions, partially including diabetes, heart disease, and lung disease such as emphysema, worsen during exposure to extreme heat raising sufferers' risk for adverse outcomes including mortality. However, the relative increase in risk is not equivalent and fine-tuning the Risk Index for each disease will provide specific value for both clinicians and sufferers.

- Confirm a heat inflection point.

The sharp spike in deaths in both Chicago and Vancouver during extreme heat events suggests that at a certain temperature deaths and hospitalizations start to increase exponentially to temperature. The inflection point may be around 130 degrees, however, given the risks involved, it may be prudent to develop clarity on this inflection point.

- Consider pedestrian traffic.

Walking is a mainstay of life in NYC. This analysis does not account for variations in average walking speed due to congested foot traffic, which can increase the time exposed to heat.

- Consideration for the homeless.

Consideration should be given to the homeless population that lives on the street especially considering that pavement temperatures can rise above 150 degrees, which can be deadly in a short period of time especially for substance abusers and those mentally ill. This was the case in Phoenix where most heat related fatalities occurred among the homeless.

- Consider for evacuation as a mitigation measure.

Given that heat waves within the United States have increased in the past several decades, some consideration for the more drastic measure of mass evacuation may be warranted. One effective way to avoid exposure to extreme heat is to simply evacuate populations cities and regions experiencing extreme and prolonged heat to cooler cities. Several considerations need to be carefully evaluated before exercising such an option. For instance, while evacuation can be an effective way to avoid exposure, especially for the most at-risk communities, and is used for natural disasters such as hurricanes and wildfires, evacuations are less practical the longer the time period involved.

A cost-benefit analysis would need to be made between the options of having populations stay indoors for the necessary hours or days, versus leaving the area altogether which will be accompanied by a reduction in economic activity in the evacuated region. Keeping individuals indoors requires the population have adequate air conditioning and that the local electric grid can facilitate its substantially increased use. Recent brown outs and black outs in summer months in hot cities suggests this may not always be the case. However, cities and regions where the electric grid is suspect may consider also that infrastructure projects to improve the viability of the power grid may represent a positive economic growth opportunity. Until such factors are carefully considered, any decision on evacuation from hot cities may best be left to the individual level.

- Understand extreme heat's impact on our oceans.

Extreme heat truly impacts One Health as higher temperatures impact all creatures and ecosystems. The OGC and its sponsors should consider extending the Urban Heat-Health Risk Index to marine environments to understand the impact rising temperatures have on sea life and the blue economy.

Appendix A – Health Impacts of Extreme Heat

Prolonged exposure to solar radiation and extreme atmospheric temperatures without opportunities for cooling, including for example, shade, can have a devastating effect on human wellbeing in both direct and indirect ways impact the health of our bodies in a myriad of ways.

Figure 9: Heat Impacts are Felt Globally and across all Age Groups.

Direct Effects

Human health can be directly impacted by excessive heat in the following ways:

Heat exhaustion and death

The most obvious and direct cause of harm from excessive heat is the morbidity and mortality created by the direct effect of heat on human bodies. Heat waves are routinely some of the deadliest natural disasters known with heat waves killing twice as many Americans as tornadoes (National Weather Service 2022).

The mortality due to heat waves is now frequently reaching into the many tens of thousands. The European heat wave of 2003 for example, is estimated to have caused 70,000 deaths (Climate Signals 2003) and the heat waves that struck Russia in 2011 killed about 56,000 Russians (Guttermann 2010). Additional information on historical heat waves appears on [Wikipedia](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Heat_wave).

Such deadly heat waves engulfing multiple countries has become routine in the last decade. There were heat waves lasting for days at a time and killing thousands in the United Kingdom (2018), United States

(2018), Japan (2018), Australia (2019), India (2019), Pakistan (2019), the European Union (2019) and India (2022) among many others (Regan 2020).

Acute kidney injury and chronic kidney disease

Excessive heat and subsequent dehydration is a major contributing factor to acute kidney injuries (AKIs) which have become epidemic among workers who toil outdoors throughout the planet and are exposed to frequent and ever more intense heat waves (Borg and Bi 2021).

A study performed in California showed that 12% of farm workers developed signs of kidney injury over the course of just a single day exposed to unrelenting heat (Moyce et al. 2020).

In Central America alone, we have seen a spike a chronic kidney disease (CKD) and eventual kidney among sugarcane workers in Central America, with CKD prevalence rising tenfold in men and fourfold in women since the 1970s (Cerdas 2005) and over 20,000 workers dying of renal failure as of 2021 (Correa-Rotter et al. 2014).

Mental health effects

Excessive heat has a palpable and measurable effect on mental health as well with heat waves affecting mood disorders, anxiety disorders, dementia, alcohol and drug misuse and suicidal behavior (Belova 2022) as well as worsening symptoms of schizophrenia in both outpatient and inpatient settings (American Psychiatric Association 2021).

Rising temperatures and humidity are related to increased emergency room visits for mental health effects (Mullins and White 2019) and increased admissions to psychiatric hospitals (Peng et al. 2017).

Heat also highly correlates with interpersonal violence and conflict between people. Multiple studies have shown positive associations between rising temperatures and increase in intentional homicides, sex offenses and assaults (Mahendran et al. 2021).

Excessive heat has also been shown to affect learning potential, with research showing an average temperature increase of just 0.55 degrees Celsius over a year resulted in a 1% decrease in learning and an accumulated \$25,000 in lost earnings for the students affected (Goodman et al. 2019) and a one-standard-deviation increase in temperature during the exam period within counties (2 °C/3.6 °F) decreasing total test scores by 0.68% (Zivin et al. 2020).

Indirect Effects

Excessive heat can also affect human health through its indirect effects. Discussed below, these effects can be longer term and therefore harder to tie to instances of extreme heat and potentially harder to mitigate.

Oceanic processes

Heat waves are just as deadly when they occur on oceans, leading to massive die offs of marine species as well as the destruction of fragile marine ecosystems such as coral (Gibbens 2019).

This has a devastating effect on biodiversity which particularly impacts sea-based economies and nutrition of oceanic origins which account for a sizable amount of the nutrition intake of much of the world's population.

Increasing heat and subsequent increased ocean temperatures have also been correlated with the increase in harmful algal blooms (Cressey 2017), increased ocean acidification (Harvey 2017) and increase in both the intensity and frequency of extreme weather of oceanic origin such as hurricanes and typhoons (Berardelli 2019).

Agricultural output, animal husbandry, and human nutrition

High temperatures have been shown to lead to decreased photosynthesis, leaf senescence, decreased pollen production and pollen viability, seed abortion, and consequently lower grain number and grain weight, particularly in some of the world's most important crops such as soy, sorghum and wheat, creating the possibility of lower yields, food shortages and global hunger (Siebert and Frank 2014).

Excessive heat stress effects on domesticated animals include reduced milk productivity, reduced fertility, increased susceptibility to disease, and increased mortality (Godde et al. 2021).

Direct heat waves effects can also lead to massive mortality among animal species important for human nutrition with a recent heat wave in Kansas estimated to have killed 10,000 heads of cattle across the state after 4 days of continuous > 104 degree heat (Myers 2022).

Bacterial infection risk and antimicrobial resistance

Horizontal gene transfer, a major mechanism for the acquisition of antibiotic resistance, is increased by increasing temperatures. In addition, increases in temperature generally increase bacterial growth rates (Pietikäinen 2005).

Increases in temperature are associated with increases in bacterial infections. An international study of 22 cities found that proximity to the equator and socioeconomic factors were both positively associated with risk of Gram-negative bacteremia (Fisman et al. 2014).

Increase in local temperatures is associated with antibiotic resistant infections. An increase in temperature of 10 °C across regions was associated with an increase in antibiotic resistance of 4.2%, 2.2%, and 2.7% for the common pathogens *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (MacFadden et al. 2018).

Vector-borne disease risk

Rising temperatures are well known to favor the growth in populations of multiple vectors known to carry disease, such as mosquitos and ticks. As temperatures increase, the range of many vectors also gets larger, increasing the number of susceptible individuals (Climate Nexus).

In the United States alone, mosquito season has grown by 76% in major cities since the 1980s due to increases in average temperatures (Kenward 2016).

It is estimated that given current climate change and increasing heat projections, the range of *Aedes aegypti*, an invasive mosquito vector for many arboviruses such as dengue, zika and yellow fever, will expand 2-6 km per year in the next 30 years (Iwamura et al. 2020).

Further modeling shows that given current warming trends, 8.4 billion people, or 90% of the projected population, will be at risk for dengue infection in 2080 due to expanded vector ranges (Udasin 2021).

Wildfire risk

Heat waves considerably increase the risk of wildfires. Short term droughts and heat waves dry out vegetation, creating perfect conditions for easy ignition and fire propagation (Borunda 2020).

Wildfires have been increasing in intensity and frequency, with significant subsequent damage to human populations, both directly through fire damage and physical burns, as well as well indirectly through smoke production and inhalation, which has been shown to increase all-cause morbidity and mortality, beyond even respiratory causes (Environmental Protection Agency 2021).

Appendix B – Leveraging Official Death Certificates for Heat-related Mortality

There is concern that low numbers of deaths officially ascribed to “excess heat” may paint a picture where rising temperatures are not a potential killer and thus not a major problem deserving of intervention.

This stems from the cause of death classification on official death certificates and the National Death Index. Typically, “heat stroke” and/or “heat exhaustion” is likely only assigned as the primary cause of death in patients who do not have any other medical conditions as a diagnosis of exclusion.

Limiting deaths to the primary cause may not be advisable when it comes to assessing the impact on health outcomes from prolonged exposure to extreme heat. The challenge is that official death certificates may not be designed to capture the degree to which heat contributed to patient mortality.

Currently, there is no objective and standardized methodology to classify the contribution from heat exposure to the medical issue that led to death. Clinicians in the United States are – purposefully – constrained regarding what they can write on death reports as the primary cause of death. If an individual succumbs to Ischemic heart disease brought on by exposure to heat, it is important to recognize the heart condition as the primary cause of death – and also important to recognize the contribution the heat exposure played in bringing on a fatal cardiac event. By recognizing the interaction of both factors, clinicians, health systems, communities, as well as individual patients will be in a better position to serve their medical needs.

Similarly, patients with chronic conditions such as COPD or renal failure will only have excess heat as a contributory cause if it’s recognized at all as a causative factor. Perhaps in addition to a contributory cause field on death certificates, such causes can be labeled as “precipitating”?

This is at the heart of why heat death counts show such variability. ([NYC, EH Data Portal, 2022 Heat-related Mortality Report](#)). In this regard, it may be better to think of excess heat like air pollution. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the majority of public health organization recognizes the deadly effect of air pollution. A recent WHO report states that air pollution is responsible for 13 deaths every minute across the planet. (WHO, Health Consequences of Air Pollution on Populations, June 2024).

However, air pollution is rarely listed as the ultimate cause of death. Instead, respiratory failure secondary to COPD exacerbation, hypoxia secondary to asthma attack, or similar, is listed even though these events were likely activated by excessive air pollution. No researcher or health professional would deny that air pollution played a major factor in these deaths.

Until additional guidance, such as from the WHO or CDC, is provided on the issue of heat-induced or heat-contributed deaths, it remains important to use both official death certificate information (with heat as the primary and contributory cause), as well as a calculation of excess deaths. This approach will better convey the overall risk. A geographic area or population that is recognized as being at risk for excessive heat harm is at risk from both direct deaths as well as deaths from chronic conditions that are worsened by prolonged heat exposure.

Appendix C - Excess Death Calculation

Excess death is an assessment of fatalities above a normal mortality rate due to a particular event of cause. An excess death calculation was used for years 2018-2023, as 2018 is the first year releasing death data by week rather than by month, to characterize a relationship between temperature and heat-related health outcomes. Analysis stratified by ICD-10 code groups¹ and demographic categories found the strongest association between extreme heat and ischemic heart diseases (ICD-10 codes I20-I25). This relationship began to curve sharply upward at a maximum daily temperature of 90°F, but due to NYC’s limited history with extreme heatwaves, calculations for max daily temperatures sustained across a full Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report (MMWR) only reached 93°F. This implies an exponential relationship but does not provide enough data for reliable extrapolation.

To estimate the rate of change beyond 93°F, data from the Pacific Northwest surrounding the 2021 heat dome was incorporated to provide a comparison, though the regions may not have an identical or similar climate environment or underlying health posture. Data was initially retrieved for Seattle and Portland, however, Multnomah County’s smaller population (795,000) provided limited information above suppression thresholds compared to King County (2.267 million).

Figure 10. Excess Deaths due to cardiovascular disease by Humidex for Seattle, WA from 2018-2023; each color band is one standard deviation.

Each ICD-10 group with enough samples to surpass suppression thresholds was plotted at individual temperatures with the median number of excess deaths in weeks recorded at that temperature. Then the

¹ ICD-10 codes are the 10th revision of the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems system used to classify and code diagnoses, symptoms and procedures for claims processing, and is maintained by the World Health Organization.

points were fitted to a polynomial. To apply these models to New York, excess deaths were converted to a percent increase above the MMWR week’s norm. This included the following conditions:

- Malignant neoplasms (C00-C97)
- Major cardiovascular diseases (I00-I78)
- Accidents (unintentional injuries) (V01-X59,Y85-Y86)
- All other diseases (Residual)

The above values were extracted by the National Death Index (NDI), accessed through CDC Wonder. Figure 8 shows a similar overall risk levels at higher temperatures between cardiovascular disease and malignant neoplasms suggesting heat has adverse impact on health outcomes broadly.

Figure 11: Comparison of Excess Death Rate at Humidex (°F) for Malignant Neoplasms (left) and cardiovascular disease (right) in Seattle, Washington for years 2018-2023.

Climate Data Calculations

Results were more consistent using minimum temperature rather than maximum or averaging the two, so humidex was calculated from minimum temperature recorded every hour or at 3 hours intervals, depending on the station, between 7 AM and 5 PM. Humidex was calculated from 22 weather stations within and surrounding Seattle, then each station was aggregated by its weekly median. Humidex is calculated in Kelvin using air temperature and dewpoint temperature, then converted to Fahrenheit for display.

$$H = T_{air} + 0.5555 \left\{ 6.11 \times \exp \left[5417.7530 * \left(\frac{1}{273.16} - \frac{1}{T_{dew}} \right) \right] - 10 \right\}$$

Where:

T_{air} = Air Temperature in Kelvin

T_{dew} = Dewpoint Temperature in Kelvin

Estimated hyperlocal humidex was interpolated from these points to Census tract centroids for each MMWR week in 2018 through 2023. Census tract polygons were also clipped from Climate Adaptation Planning and Analytics (CAPA) surface temperature raster files of ground measurements shown in Figure 9 for Census tract 53033030902 in King County, Washington.

Figure 12: CAPA surface temperature for Census tract 53033030902 in King County, WA.

Surface data was centered around a 0 median and added to the interpolated temperature layer. The x- and y- axes on the graph in Figure 10 represent longitude and latitude, respectively.

Figure 13: Interpolated Humidex, surface observations, and heat distribution, respectively, for week 18 in 2020 for Seattle, WA.

Model Output

Central Park is on average 3.7°F cooler than the rest of the study area. Correlation analysis estimates a typical minimum temperature corresponding to a 103.7°F maximum in Manhattan would be around 89°F. Keeping a steady dewpoint value of 71.3°F (equivalent to 40% relative humidity at 100°F), this gives a model input of 101.5°F minimum humidex value. The model output returns a rate of excess deaths in that group for the specified temperature.

The median number of deaths in Manhattan during the summer for each group was multiplied by the corresponding model output and adjusted proportionally to represent death counts over 5 days instead of 7. This estimates scenario 1 would result in 92 to 170 excess deaths due to disease and accidental injury. The range depends on the type of interpolation used to aggregate median temperature, temperature range used to fit the polynomial, and method to estimate a minimum humidex value at scenario maximum and relative humidity. These values and the overall range may be an underestimate as this analysis utilized only the primary cause of death to avoid double counting any particular death in multiple record requests. When death certificates are returned to include all contributing causes of death, similar correlation curves are found in death records with codes for diabetes and mental disorders.

Social Determinants of Health

To identify most affected Census tracts, estimated temperature at each tract was put into a regression model measuring the strength of correlation between that tracts' temperature and county-level deaths. The R value for each tract was then used as the dependent variable in an analysis of associated social and health variables at the tract level. Most associated variables differed between ICD-10 groups, but percent of renter-occupied dwellings and percent of population over age over 65 were found to have a strong positive correlation in each model. Percentage of commuters who drove alone to work had a strong negative correlation. While correlation strength for each disease code group could indicate higher or lower risk of excess deaths in each category, the level of abstraction makes applying these factors as a numeric increase or decrease across the study population impractical. However, it is strongly suggestive that heat exacerbates numerous common medical conditions to the point of potential mortality and further analysis towards determining an inflection point at which the rate of risk rises is warranted.

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